

CREATIVE COMPONENT OF THE PROFESSIONAL AND PEDAGOGICAL CULTURE OF FUTURE TEACHERS

Ibraimova Feruza Xolboyevna

Doctoral student at Uzbekistan scientific research institute of pedagogical sciences named after
T.N. Kori Niyazi

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Modern science and creativity are considered by many researchers to be integral, basic components of culture. The problem of relations between personality, culture, and creativity is reflected in the works of N.A. Berdyaev. Considering the global problem of the interaction of civilization and culture, he believed that in a certain sense, civilization is older and more fundamental than culture: civilization means a social-collective process, and culture is more individual; it is a person related to creative activity. N. A. Berdyaev saw his skillful nature in the creation of culture by the creative action of a person: "Creativity is fire; culture is the cooling of fire." The creative act is in the space of subjectivity, and the cultural product is in objective reality.

The creative nature of pedagogical activity determines a special style of mental activity of the teacher, which is related to the novelty and significance of his results and brings about a complex synthesis of all mental areas of the teacher's personality (cognitive, emotional, volitional, and motivational). A special place in it is the developed need for creation embodied in specific abilities and their manifestation. One of these abilities is the integrative and highly differentiated ability of pedagogical thinking. The ability of pedagogical thinking, which is different in nature and content, allows the teacher to actively change the pedagogical information beyond the limits of the temporary parameters of pedagogical reality. The effectiveness of a teacher's professional activity depends not only on knowledge and skills but also on the ability to use information given in a pedagogical situation in different ways and at a fast pace. A developed intellect allows the teacher to study not only individual pedagogical facts and events but also pedagogical ideas and the theory of teaching and educating students. Reflectiveness, humanism, orientation to the future, and a clear understanding of the tools necessary for professional improvement and the development of the student's personality are characteristic features of the intellectual competence of the teacher. Advanced pedagogical thinking, which provides a deep semantic understanding of pedagogical information and breaks down the methods of knowledge and activity through the prism of one's own professional and pedagogical experience, helps to acquire the personal meaning of professional activity.

The personal meaning of professional activity requires sufficient activity from the teacher and the ability to manage and regulate his behavior in accordance with emerging or specially set pedagogical tasks. Self-regulation as a voluntary manifestation of personality reveals its nature and mechanism. Professional qualities such as a teacher's personality, initiative, independence, responsibility, etc. In psychology, as personality traits that are stable, repeated in different situations, a person's behavior characteristics are understood. In this regard, L.I. Antsyferova's point of view of including the ability to organize, control, analyze and evaluate one's behavior in accordance with the motives that drive one's behavior is worthy of attention. According to him, the more familiar this or that behavior is, the more generalized and automated this skill becomes. Such an understanding of the genesis of traits allows us to present integrated acts of activity with the psychological dominant states that arise on their basis as the basis of these formations. A

creative person is characterized by readiness to take risks, independence in reasoning, impulsivity, cognitive "attention", critical judgments, originality, boldness of imagination and thought, sense of humor and tendency to humor, etc. These reveal the characteristics of a truly free, independent, and active person, as emphasized by AN Luk.

Pedagogik ijod bir qator xususiyatlarga ega (V.I.Zag-vyazinskiy, N.D.Nikandrov):

➤ Pedagogical creativity has a number of characteristics (V.I. Zag-Vyazinsky, N.D. Nikandrov): It is more organized in time and space. The stages of the creative process (the emergence of a pedagogical concept, development, realization of meaning, etc.) are tightly connected with each other in time, requiring an operative transition from one stage to another;

➤ If, in the activity of a writer, artist, or scientist, pauses between stages of creative activity are very acceptable, often even necessary, in the professional activity of a teacher, they are practically excluded;

➤ The teacher is limited by the number of hours allotted to study a particular subject, section, etc. During the educational session, there are expected and unforeseen problem situations that require a competent solution, the quality of which may limit the choice of the best solution due to the psychological specificity of solving pedagogical problems;

➤ delay of the teacher's creative research In the field of material and spiritual activity, its result is immediately realized and can be connected with the goal, and the results of the teacher's work are embodied in the knowledge, skills, abilities, forms of activity, and behavior of the students and are evaluated very partially and relatively. This situation makes it difficult to make a valid decision at a new stage of pedagogical activity. The developed analytical, prognostic, reflective, and other abilities of the teacher allow him to foresee and predict the result of his professional and pedagogical activities based on partial results;

➤ based on the unity of purpose in professional activity, the teacher's creation together with students and colleagues in the pedagogical process The atmosphere of creative research in the teams of teachers and students is a strong motivating factor. The teacher, as an expert in a certain field of knowledge, shows his students his creative attitude toward professional activity during the educational process.

➤ the dependence of the creative pedagogical potential of the teacher on the methodological and technical equipment of the educational process. Standard and non-standard educational and research equipment, technical support, teacher's methodological preparation, and psychological preparation of students for joint research characterize the unique features of pedagogical creativity;

➤ the ability to manage the personal emotional and psychological state of the teacher and to induce adequate behavior in the students' activities. The teacher's ability to organize communication with students as a creative process without suppressing their initiative and ingenuity, creating conditions for full creative expression and self-realization.

The identified characteristics of pedagogical creativity allow us to better understand the conditionality of combining algorithmic and creative components of pedagogical activity. The nature of creative pedagogical work is such that it includes certain features of normative activity. Pedagogical activity is creative when algorithmic activity does not give the desired results. Algorithms, methods, and methods of normative pedagogical activity mastered by the teacher are included in many non-standard, unexpected situations, the solution of which requires constant waiting, change, correction, and regulation, which encourages the teacher to demonstrate

innovative activity. pedagogical way of thinkingThe question of the ability to teach creativity is quite legitimate. Such opportunities lie, first of all, in the part that constitutes the normative basis of pedagogical activity: knowledge of the laws of the holistic pedagogical process, knowledge of the goals and tasks of joint activities, readiness for self-study and self-improvement, etc.

Pedagogical creativity does not appear by itself as a component of professional pedagogical culture. A favorable cultural and creative environment, a stimulating environment, and objective and subjective conditions are necessary for its development. As one of the most important objective conditions for the development of pedagogical creativity, we consider the influence of socio-cultural and pedagogical reality and the specific cultural-historical conditions that the teacher creates in a certain period. Without recognizing and understanding this situation, it is impossible to understand the true essence, source, and means of implementation of pedagogical creativity. Other objective conditions include a positive emotional and psychological climate in the team; the level of development of scientific knowledge in psychological, pedagogical, and special fields; the availability of appropriate educational and training facilities; the scientific validity of methodological recommendations and instructions; the material and technical equipment of the pedagogical process; and the availability of socially necessary time.

The subjective conditions for the development of pedagogical creativity are as follows: knowledge of the basic laws and principles of the integral pedagogical process; a high level of general cultural training of the teacher; modern concepts of education and training; the ability to analyze typical situations and make decisions in such situations; striving for creativity; developing pedagogical thinking and reflection; pedagogical experience and intuition; the ability to make operational decisions in atypical situations; having a problematic view; and pedagogical technology. Therefore, personal characteristics and creativity are manifested in various forms and methods of creative self-awareness by the teacher. Self-awareness works as a field of application for the individual creative abilities of a person. The problem of pedagogical creativity has a direct connection to the problem of self-awareness in the teacher. Therefore, pedagogical creativity is the process of self-awareness of the individual, psychological, and intellectual powers and abilities of a teacher.

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